

Review Based Analysis on Application of Relaxation Measures in All Age Groups To Alleviate Chronic Pain

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: *The purpose of this study is to find out the effectiveness of comprehensive methods of relaxation techniques in reducing the chronic pain and improving the quality of life. Pain is an unpleasant feeling making life more difficult causing psychological distress. Pain may be presented in many different ways; intense, sharp, nagging, burning, dull, unbearable, tender and so on. It may be classified into acute and chronic pain depending upon the duration of the pain one experiences. It is very individualized experience with varied perception of pain and tolerance or threshold of a person. The pain which lasts more than 3 months is considered as chronic pain. The mental health of an individual is disturbed to a certain extent with the chronic pain as such it may push them to suffer from stress and depression.*

Design /Methodology/Approach: *Secondary data collected using Google search engine here. Many authors used many a different methods namely randomized control trial, systematic review and meta-analysis of literatures, evidence based therapeutic intervention.*

Finding /Result: *There are certain non-pharmacological relaxation methods practiced to relieve the chronic pain namely; progressive relaxation technique, Benson relaxation technique, mindfulness-meditation and so on. Through this article we are going to review articles using Google search engine where they used the relaxation techniques on chronic pain sufferers from different age groups of adults and children. The efficacy of relaxation methods are also discussed in alleviating chronic pain. Several other benefits such as reduction in anxiety and depression, improvement on overall wellbeing and better coping methods or strategies were also studied in this analysis. The effective relaxation techniques showed significant improvement in the reduction of chronic pain in a long run, when practiced regularly and they are more popular because they are easy to learn and practice. At the same time one can select the convenient comprehensive measure of their choice.*

Originality/ Value: *The relaxation techniques practiced in every reviewed article is different and effective. The main selected measures are; progressive relaxation technique, Benson relaxation technique, mindfulness-meditation. These comprehensive techniques are available without any financial burden and easy to practice.*

Paper Type: *Secondary source research review and analysis.*

Key Words: *Chronic pain, Depression, Meditation, Quality of life, Relaxation technique,*

1. INTRODUCTION:

1.1 Chronic pain is one; it lasts longer than at least three months. It may limit many interactions with family, friends or society. A Norway study revealed, the chronic pain suffering population was 50%. As per the reviewed articles, chronic pain relief with only pharmacological treatment showed limited relief and increased dependency. Pain is thus considered as perceived by an individual as both subjective experience and a physical sensation with individual differences. The only non-pharmacological, comprehensive treatment in pain relief is Relaxation Technique. [1] **Pain** is defined as ‘the unpleasant emotional and sensory experience by actual or possible tissue damage’. The pain is multi-dimensional and always experienced by every individual in a unique way. **Chronic**

pain is simply defined as the persistent pain beyond the expected period of healing or lasts more than 3-6 months. [2] Chronic Pain can result in distress and suffering. [3]

1.2. Relaxation Measures

The main relaxation methods used to relieve chronic pain in these reviewed articles are progressive relaxation technique, autogenic training, breathing exercise, guided imagery and meditation using randomized control trials. Most of the studies showed significant pain relief along with other benefits such as improvement in anxiety, depression, better coping strategy and quality of life. [1] Using relaxation is a reliable and positive method of making progress in managing pain. It makes one feel good and helps to sleep naturally. The more one practices relaxation measures, the better results so it is better to stick with it. Relaxation can also reduce the feelings of stress by helping to gain more control over our feelings. Relaxation measures are normally reducing pain by decreasing muscle tension, aches and pains. Relaxation enhances the release of endorphins ('the body's natural pain-killers') to relieve pain. Promote sleep by allowing the body to rest peacefully and calm the mind. [4] The relaxation measures are of many varieties and all of them working in reduction of pain with regular practice by slowing down breathing and reducing heart rate, blood pressure. [5] Relaxation skills might take long time to learn and get accustomed to it. But once we get hold of it, it will reduce the feelings of daily stress, any chronic long lasting pain by reducing the muscle tension, aches etc. It also helps in release of endorphins to relieve pain. Promotion of sleep is the main benefit too. [6] The absence of harmful side effects in relaxation therapy and no stringent training needed to train the clients, relaxation is becoming more effective and popular. [7] American Psychological Association in an article regarding stress states that, every organ in the human body gets affected by regular stress and strain on a regular basis leading to chronic pain including wear and tear. Making time for oneself to the relaxation measures could improve the quality of life. [8] Relaxation techniques are effective only when practiced regularly on pain control. [9] Relaxation measures come under complementary health category interventions. [6]

1.3. Progressive Muscle Relaxation technique

Progressive muscle relaxation is a technique and by practice it relieves tension. In here we need to tense a group of muscles during inhalation. The process of sudden relaxation of muscle group follows. Working on muscle groups in a certain order will be helpful. Physical relaxation aids in reduction of feeling anxious. Practicing progressive muscle relaxation for a few weeks will help to get better at this skill, and in time one will be able to use this method to relieve stress. If one has trouble falling asleep, this method may also help with the sleep problems. The reviewed studies had methodology issues, so they were inconclusive about interventions. Suggested further research to confirm positive findings related to relaxation. The other relaxation techniques require carefully designed trials. [10]

- Breathe in, tense the first muscle group of one's choice, it could be fist or toes/foot for few seconds.
- Breathe out then do a sudden total relaxation of the muscle group which was selected to breathe in. Gradual relaxation is not allowed. Relax for few seconds before starting to work on the next set of muscle group. It is advisable to feel the difference between the tensed muscles and the relaxed muscle group to compare.
- Keep these same processes going until the muscle groups are finished doing tense and relaxation process, then relax to normal state. [11]

1.4. Benson Relaxation Technique is coined by Dr. Herbert Benson the word 'relaxation response' by removing the mysterious word meditation and brought this Benson relaxation technique to the main stream. He is a professor, author, founder of Harvard's Mind/Body Medical Institute and cardiologist. This relaxation technique is defined as the ability of a person to encourage the body to release chemicals and brain signals that make muscles and organs to slow down thereby increasing the blood flow to the brain. The concentration on deep breathing and continuous practice help to reduce anxiety as per many studies in different health related conditions. He stated that regular practice of the Relaxation Response can be an effective treatment for a wide range of stress-related disorders. Using relaxation is beneficial as it counteracts with stress and anxiety. [12] Benson Relaxation Technique is effective in reduction of pain intensity after intervention. [13]

1.5. Mindful meditation is a combined practice of meditation and mind-fullness; it is a mental training to slow down the racing thoughts and thereby reducing anxiety. In chronic pain when practiced deep breathing and relaxation with body awareness the studies showed small effect on pain symptoms improvement. But mindful-meditation showed significant improvement in quality of life by improving depression. [14] Physical functioning would not change with the practice of mindfulness. The chronic pain sufferers normally try to ignore the pain. But by practicing mindfulness they challenge by increasing attention to pain and relating the pain in a different way thereby trying to reduce the use of analgesia. [15]

2. RELATED WORKS:

The reviewed articles regarding the comprehensive relaxation measures all throw light on managing pain without analgesics to some extent. Some authors say that the relaxation measures can be useful as an adjuvant therapy in chronic pain sufferers. Most of the articles suggest practicing these measures regularly as a part of the daily routine to get the optimum effect. As we know in olden days the yoga and meditation they practiced for the human wellbeing. Now it is time to implement meditation/ relaxation back in our daily activities as they don't only serve the purpose of pain control but also promote quality of life. The articles were supporting the different techniques of relaxation measures, some of them are progressive muscle relaxation, deep breathing exercises, meditation etc. Over all the studies support the benefits of application of relaxation measures in all age groups.

S. No	Title of the Article	Focus area / Findings	Reference
1	<i>“Relaxation techniques as an intervention for chronic pain: A systematic review of randomized controlled trials”.</i>	They concluded in their review analysis that the relaxation techniques may be more effective if they are practiced regularly and in a long run. They insisted to perform future studies to investigate long term effects and the efficacy differences between different pain conditions. Other benefits such as reduction in anxiety and depression, overall well being and better coping methods/strategies.	Sara Magelsen et al, (2021) [1]
2	<i>“Cognitive Change and Relaxation as Key Mechanisms of Treatment Outcome in Chronic Pain”.</i>	Their data demonstrated some associations of changes in coping skills with pain, and reduction in disability and depression after using the relaxation measures along with cognitive restructuring. The findings cautiously stated that clinicians need to optimize processes in cognitive change and relaxation to reduce chronic pain.	Matthias Feldmann et al, (2021), [16]
3	<i>“Association Between Psychological Interventions and Chronic Pain Outcomes in Older Adults A Systematic Review and Meta-analysis”.</i>	The efficacy of the results of interventions is very little and they suggested more studies required to come to a strong conclusion. Group approaches were more effective when compared to one on one treatment. Chronic pain is considered as one of the commonest among elderly and disabled people. Suggested conducting more robust interventional measures to relieve and reduce pain non-pharmacologically.	BaharNiknejad, MD et al, (2018) [17]
4	<i>“Evidence-Based Psychological Interventions for the Management of Pediatric Chronic Pain: New Directions in Research and Clinical Practice”.</i>	Cognitive reframing, bio-behavioral relaxation, graded in vivo exposure, and mindfulness are demonstrated to decrease pain. The main goal of these interventions is, to improve functioning and self-efficacy, and then reduce the daily stress that co-occurs in children and adolescents with persistent pain. Not found out any one relaxation measure working on all children with chronic pain. The patho-physiology, environmental influence, and family background everything is unique to every individual. There is a vast requirement of models of care which is flexible with limited resources.	Rachael Coakley and Tessa Wihak, (2017), [18]
5	<i>“Psychological interventions influence patients' attitudes and</i>	Psycho-education and physiotherapy along with self hypnosis and self care learning were applied and compared with control group. The	Audrey Vanhudenhuysen et al, (2017) [19]

	<i>beliefs about their chronic pain”.</i>	interventions were showing significant effects in evolution of coping mechanisms from passive to active. Also proved to improve anxiety and depression related symptoms associated with chronic pain and improved quality of life too.	
6	<i>“The role of psychological interventions in the management of patients with chronic pain”.</i>	The efficacy of behavioral, self-regulatory and other cognitive techniques were studied. The psychologists noticed the difference in their pain control and how effectively the relaxation techniques help patients in gaining the command over their pain control and assisted in leading a better quality life. The implementation of psychological interventions with great skills; they aided in enabling the patients to become active participants in the management of their own illness. The psychologist’s efforts would be to instill valuable skills that patients can practice throughout their lives.	Daniela Roditi et al (2011) [2]
7	<i>“Relaxation and Mindfulness in Pain”.</i>	Mindfulness is on purpose, non-judgmental attention in a particular way. Relaxation is attaining a psycho-physiological state or hyp-arousal. The methods used in the reviewed articles are progressive muscle/muscular relaxation, autogenic training, biofeedback and guided imagery. These measures unfortunately did not show the expected significance in reducing acute or chronic pain. During the follow up with chronic pain the evidences proved that the usefulness reduced over time.	Emma Dun ford, (2010) [20]

3. OBJECTIVES:

The article is prepared to shed light on the comprehensive measures of relaxation techniques used regularly and the efficacy of the techniques in reducing chronic pain. Though people are aware of regular relaxation measures but seldom practice them. We instead use some pain killers as it is easily accessible. Through this article I would like to create awareness about the benefits without any economical burden.

1. To know the benefits of relaxation techniques in reducing the chronic pain and improving quality of life.
2. To identify the better techniques that may be used in reduction of chronic pain.
3. To identify the efficacy of the relaxation techniques used in chronic pain sufferers.
4. To identify the relation between relaxations measures in relieving pain rather than analgesics.

4. METHODOLOGY:

Review of literature was done using secondary data through search key words ‘relaxation technique’, ‘meditation’, ‘quality of life’, ‘chronic pain’, ‘depression’. Electronic Data gathered through Google Scholar and Research Gate. Systematic review was performed selecting the articles from 2010 to 2021.

5. NEW RELATED ISSUES:

The reviewed articles about chronic pain and the measures taken to alleviate pain clearly states that clients desperately in need for some non-pharmacological measures which cause lesser economic burden and easy to practice. Treatment of chronic pain during the longer time duration; where they are suffering from chronic pain the psychologists or social workers may play a major role in transforming their life by introducing any one of the relaxation techniques to their daily routine. These measures normally proved to have better effects if they are using the relaxation measures as discussed above on a regular basis for good long time. Along with pain relief these measures are effectively reducing the level of anxiety, stress and depression aiding better quality of life. Once the patient is diagnosed to have a chronic pain they will be screened regularly for any psychological issues. Any one of relaxation measure needs to be implemented as an adjuvant therapy at this aspect. The articles reviewed above proved the efficacy of relaxation methods on children, adults and elderly.

6. IDEAL SOLUTIONS, CURRENT STATUS AND IMPROVEMENTS REQUIRED:

Educating the client about the available options of relaxation measures is important and to make them understand that they are easy to practice and without financial burden on the family. The other benefits of relaxation are also explained in reducing stress. For some clients the relaxation measures will help to relieve pain without requiring pharmacology treatment. But for others might require analgesics concurrently. The chronic pain along with distress may cause social isolation and might require counseling to understand the requirement of mindfulness or meditation with relaxation. The non pharmacological treatments with no side effects need to be reinforced in medical field as an adjuvant therapy aiding to relaxation. The life has become stressful for everyone in all age groups and people are always on their toes in this competitive world. It is a requirement of each and every human being, not only the chronic pain sufferer to practice simple relaxation measures for the future wellbeing.

7. RESEARCH GAP:

1. Research gap here is to find out any single specific relaxation measure used to relieve chronic pain in the reviewed articles.
2. To identify a specific relaxation technique that is easy to practice in reduction of chronic pain.
3. There are many relaxation techniques as mentioned above namely Benson's relaxation technique and progressive muscle relaxation, Mindful meditation, out of these which will be the best in improving the wellbeing by alleviating pain needs to be studied further.

8. RECOMMENDATIONS:

- (1) The perception of level of pain needs to be reduced by using the relaxation techniques.
- (2) The basic causes of chronic pain needs to be investigated, whether it is physical, mental or both together.
- (3) Understanding the importance of regular practice of relaxation techniques.
- (4) Improving the patient's awareness about the chronic pain and the relaxation measures and its benefits would help them to schedule regular practice.
- (5) Giving feedback and the discussion with fellow clients about relaxation techniques will improve confidence in other fellow clients.

9. ANALYSIS OF REVIEW OF RESEARCH:

- a) The reviewed articles reinforced on regular practice of the comprehensive relaxation measures.
- b) Though some of the research did not show significant effect on pain relief, some authors insisted to use these techniques as an adjuvant therapy along with analgesics.
- c) The analysis on the efficacy of relaxation methods were done on all age groups and most of the researches showed marked improvement on pain relief.
- d)

10. LIMITATIONS:

- The secondary data collected only through Google scholar search engine.
- Only limited literatures reviewed in this context. It would have been more useful in concluding the results if I have reviewed more literatures to reinforce the pain relief effect on chronic pain patients.

11. CONCLUSION:

This analysis threw light on the benefits and efficacy of relaxation measures in relieving chronic pain. The progressive relaxation measures, Breathing exercise and mindful-meditation in adult population showed marked improvement in chronic pain relief. Chronic pain is considered as the most common cause of distress and disability in the elderly population; the simple comprehensive relaxation measures practiced in this study were profitable if practiced regularly in a long run. In evidence based study on pediatric population the relaxation measures alleviated chronic pain and improved the quality of life. The persistent pain is prone to significant physical, psychosocial, and psychological burdens for children, families and the health care systems too. Cognitive reframing, bio-behavioral relaxation, graded in vivo exposure, and mindfulness-meditation are demonstrated to decrease pain, while implementing these techniques on a regular basis.

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